

PLAN-B

Tackling light and noise pollution

**Review of Communication,
Dissemination and Exploitation
Plan**

(DEC Plan) V. 2

Please refer to this report as follows:

Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation, including Communication Measures (DEC Plan) V.2

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List of Acronyms

LP	Light pollution
NP	Noise Pollution
CS	Citizen Science
TBES	Terrestrial Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
WP/WPs	Work Package(s)
T	Task
DEC Plan	Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation, including Communication Measures
M	Month(s)
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
SWOT Analysis	Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats analysis

1- Executive summary

Led by the Ibercivis Foundation (IBE), this document is the second version of the [Project Communications and Dissemination plan \(DEC Plan V.2\)](#). It builds upon the content of Deliverable 6.1, “Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation, including Communication Measures” (DEC Plan V.1), which lays the groundwork and mentions the existence of this second version (D6.2) for review and adjustment.

This initial roadmap and transversal framework for the PLAN-B project’s communication, dissemination and exploitation activities has resulted in a series of actions and activities aligned with the overall objectives of the project, confirming its robustness, while leaving room for continuous improvement after 18 months of work. The development of the project and the emergence of new partners along the way have led to new decisions being taken to ensure that the project will achieve its intended aims and gain significant scientific and social impact.

The project has gained strong visibility both within the academic sphere and beyond by engaging with institutions, research centres, and organizations operating within the ecosystem of European-funded projects with similar objectives. It has established solid connections with such projects, collectively referred to as “The PLAN-B Network”, and has successfully raised public awareness of the harmful effects of noise (NP) and light pollution (LP) on terrestrial biodiversity and ecosystem services (TBES) across Europe.

Much of the work carried out to date has focused on introducing uninitiated audiences to the issues around which the project revolves and their impacts on biodiversity and habitats, through communication and dissemination activities, workshops, and the production of graphic material.

PLAN-B’s presence in social media has been constant and consistent, which has allowed us to achieve several set objectives. Two online workshops have been successfully organised: (1) on the [project’s citizen science activity through its Lost At Night application](#) and (2) on [light pollution regulations](#), with more than 230 attendees; more than 400 subscribers to the newsletter, 6000 unique users to the website and over 500 followers on the project’s LinkedIn profile.

All this, together with the continuous collaboration between PLAN-B and closely related initiatives on projects’ activities, associations and media, has ensured the achievement of the communication objectives proposed at the beginning of the project.

2- Object of the Deliverable

- **Review, re-evaluate, and refine** the communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan established in V.1.
- **Update the tools, activity timeline, and definition of target audiences (TA) and messages** based on the experience of the first period.
- **Report** on the degree of **achievement** of the Key Performance Indicators (**KPIs**) and propose corrective measures.
- **Establish the basis** for **communication**, dissemination, and exploitation activities for the **remaining project period** (M18-M48).

3- Introduction and Updated Analysis

3.1 - Context of the PLAN-B project and the role of the DEC Plan

The elaboration and establishment of PLAN-B's communication plan, reflected in D6.1, has served as a tool for internal and external communication of the project by laying the foundations for its presence in the different communication channels chosen. It has also served to achieve a common and recognizable image in all its activities and appearances, thanks to a complete graphic image that covers all areas: website, presence in social media, presentations, attendance of dissemination activities, etc.

3.2 - Period covered by this review (M6-M18)

In addition to the general analysis of the status and performance of the measures and actions planned in the project's DEC plan, this document will reflect the results obtained during its implementation period from M6 to M18, which will serve to provide evidence of the results obtained and to propose corrective measures to align the communication activity of the project in its subsequent phases and until its closure.

3.3 - Review and update of the initial SWOT analysis

As part of the initial development of the communication plan, a preliminary SWOT analysis was carried out, which pointed out the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats for the communication strategy.

After 18 months of work, further analysis has been conducted, confirming many of the initial findings while also revealing new opportunities and potential risks. Collaboration with related projects, such as the sister project [AquaPLAN](#), has been strengthened, sharing clustering activities and providing spaces for the communication of common objectives, such as via newsletter or organised events.

Engagement from the early stages of the project with stakeholder groups, such as communities involved in the protection of quiet and dark spaces, NGOs, citizens, and policymakers, has strengthened our position on both issues in the public sphere.

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Experience in managing communication plans on previous European projects. ✓ The consortium has expert researchers in each of the project's areas of work. ✓ The consortium has social media experts and media influencers. ✓ Broad experience in writing academic papers, press releases, policy documents, and other media materials. ✓ Several consortium members are well-established in the field and possess extensive dissemination networks. ✓ The establishment of the PLAN-B Network reinforces PLAN-B's visibility and engagement within sister project activities and the broader European research landscape. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ The workload can make it difficult to spend time on communication tasks. ✗ The existence of long periods of no new scientific output is generated. that may not allow the extraction of direct information for external communication. ✗ Declining user activity on Twitter (now X) has reduced its effectiveness as a communication channel, resulting in limited growth in followers and engagement. ✗ Audience engagement is voluntary, limiting the reach of communication tools such as newsletters.

OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ LP and NP are in line with the European Green Deal, the objectives of the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and other European policy action documents. ✓ There is a wide network of organisations and institutions working on the mitigation of LP and NP impacts, with extensive experience in engagement and communication across Europe. ✓ PLAN-B has connected with LP and NP communities, activists, and organisations around the world. ✓ There is direct contact with related projects. This will help develop common communication strategies to reach larger audiences. ✓ Strong engagement and collaboration with the industry. ✓ LP and NP are gaining increasing attention on political, regulatory, and research agendas, highlighting the urgency and relevance of the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Failure to achieve the KPIs set out in the proposal. ✗ A misalignment between the timing of result delivery, milestone achievement, and the project's communication needs can hinder timely and impactful dissemination. ✗ Delays in the development or adoption of relevant EU or national regulations may reduce the project's short-term policy impact or stall implementation of proposed measures. ✗ Industry stakeholders may challenge proposed technical standards, ecological limitations and mitigation measures, citing feasibility or innovation constraints, which could slow down regulatory progress.

Table 1: SWOT Analysis

The SWOT analysis and continuous reflection enable PLAN-B to strengthen its communication and dissemination strategy, while proactively developing measures to address emerging threats. For instance, to gain the support of industry stakeholders and ensure alignment with researchers, projects, environmental organisations, and activists working on LP and NP, the PLAN-B project has fostered strong collaboration across these groups. This includes integrating representatives from each into its advisory board and organising clustering activities, such as inviting industry actors to review and disseminate the Light Pollution Policy Brief.

4 - Review and Update of the Communication Plan Setup

4.1 - Visual Image

4.1.1 - Review of the visual image

The visual image is the set of graphic resources used to create the brand of the project, with a specific and recognizable look and feel.

This set is composed of the logo, graphic resources, colours, typography and styles, together with a user manual of all these tools for use in any of the communication activities carried out by the project, both online (infographics, documents, images, etc.) and offline (signage, events, roll-ups, flyers, etc.).

During the implementation period covered by this deliverable (M1-M18), the graphic image of the project has been able to unfold to become a very recognizable element within the sphere of communities concerned with LP and NP. The decision to combine in a simple way the three key elements of the project, light, sound and biodiversity in a logo has been well received within the consortium and the choice of a moth as a distinctive element of the logo has ensured that, by avoiding elements commonly associated with the project's subject matter (owl, light bulb, siren, etc.), brand retention has been greater among our stakeholders.

The graphic image of the project has been applied in:

The project website	Internal documents, deliverables
Social media profiles (X , LinkedIn , YouTube)	Posters
Meetings	Apps
Workshops, congresses, and events	Publications
Presentations	

Table 2: Graphic Mediums where visual image has been applied.

This application is necessary to harmonize the image of the project in all its appearances. Some examples of these applications:

Table 3: Graphic material examples of PLAN-B.

4.1.2 - Changes in the logotype shape:

The application of the logo in different media and situations led to a slight adaptation towards a circular silhouette to find a better fit in spaces where this shape was obligatory, such as social network profiles. Both forms coexist seamlessly and are used interchangeably in their different formats and applications.

Figure 1: From squared to rounded logotype shape.

4.1.3 - plan-b-project.eu Web Redesign

In November 2024, PLAN-B's design and communication team redesigned the project's website, with the intention of accommodating new sections and responding to the new needs of the project, thus responding to the consortium's requirements.

The intention was to deliver a more compact and informative design after the first stage of the project, when the communication objectives were more expository. In addition, a newsletter subscription button and space for the citizen science application Lost at Night were added. Moreover, the website has a direct link to the European light pollution policy campaign launched in April 2025. More space has also been added for the blog, and the rest of the sections have been redesigned.

The project website, as a cornerstone of PLAN-B's communication strategy and content cycle, will continue to undergo regular modifications to adapt to the needs of the project.

Figure 2: Web Redesign.

4.2 - Communication Objectives

4.2.1 - Review the objectives defined in D6.1

Documentation of the project activity on its website	ok
Number of graphic resources generated for communication and dissemination	ok
Presence of the project on social media	ok
Presence of the project in traditional media	ok
Creation and maintenance of an online community around the project	ok
Attendance at the proposed activities	ok

Table 4: Communication Objectives defined in D6.1.

Documentation of the project activity on its website

Through the planned editorial calendar, the project has been able to regularly document its activity on the website's blog.

The daily activity of the project, namely the development of tasks and work packages, the attendance to events, the organisation of workshops and working sessions, the publication of articles, etc., has been joined by a series of news items related to the project's object of study, the concern about LP and NP in TBES, addressed to both expert and non-expert audiences, with the aim of raising awareness of the project, its activities, as well as LP and NP impacts

Through its blog, the project has showcased the activities of sister projects and stakeholder communities dedicated to protecting the darkest skies and the quietest ecosystems.

This table provides links to the 48 blog posts published in the period between M1 and M18 [click on title to access the post]:

PLAN-B Participates in DarkerSky4CE workshop	Travis Longcore has joined the PLAN-Biodiversity project as an advisory board member
Reinhard Klenke: The Biologist Shedding Light on Light Pollution	The Journey So Far: PLAN-B's Milestone Meeting
Telling the story of light pollution from coast to coast	[Article] Monitoring, trends and impacts of light pollution
Full recording of the PLAN-B Workshop on light pollution regulation	Defining Mechanistic Pathways for Anthropogenic Noise Impact on Avian Species
Online Workshop on Light Pollution Regulation: Meet the panellists	International Day of Light
PLAN-B in the Adrisky Project conference	PLAN-B, presented in the Beat the Big Buys podcast
Event Announcement: Online Policy Workshop on Light Pollution Regulation	The PLAN-B piloting activities starts in Gdansk to tackle noise and light pollution
[Report] Zero pollution monitoring and outlook 2025	Project meeting at Gdańsk Tech on April 18-19 for PLAN-B
The European Light Pollution Manifesto	Meet the PLAN-B consortium: The Ibercivis Foundation
The light and noise pollution issue arrives to the House of Lords	EURODARK 2024 Symposium recap
The PLAN-B hybrid event: Consortium meeting & Stakeholders workshops	PLAN-B invites you to endorse the Light Pollution Manifesto
Gdańsk Takes Action Against Light Pollution: A Step Towards a Darker, Healthier Night Sky	PLAN-B & AquaPLAN meeting
[Article] Light pollution regulations and where to find them	Dark Sky Week April 2 - 8, 2024
[The PLAN-B Network] Updates of the AquaPLAN project	[Media] Gdańsk Tech announces the launch of PLAN-B
[The PLAN-B Network] Latest updates from the Interreg North Sea DARKER SKY project	[Article] The world at night: preserving natural darkness for heritage conservation and night sky appreciation
Report: The World at Night	[Article] Why flying insects gather at artificial light
Starlight Conference 2024 - Lake Tekapo, New Zealand	AquaPLAN kick-off meeting
Belgian Council Blocks Additional Bike Path Lighting to Protect Wildlife	PLAN-B, a project to tackle light and noise pollution in European biodiversity, is launched.
Big Announcement: New Light Pollution Map of Europe	[Press Release] Launch of the PLAN-B EU-funded project to protect terrestrial biodiversity from light and noise pollution.
Brazilian partners of PLAN-B take neglected pollutants to COP 16 on Biodiversity, in Cali, Colombia	

[8-9 Nov 2024] Under One Sky gathering

Light and noise pollution issues at a music festival in Poland

[The PLAN-B Network] The Darker Sky Project: Overview of its First Year

Success in the First Citizen Science Workshop PLAN-B Project

Table 5: Links to website blogposts.

Graphic resources generated for communication and dissemination:

The image of the project has been developed in different applications: Flyers and brochures, Covers for the presentations of the project, Thumbnails for videos and Backgrounds for online presentation:

PLAN-B

PLAN-B
Tackling light and noise pollution

PLAN-B aims to bring scientific evidence to protect Europe's biodiversity and ecosystems from the adverse effects of light and noise pollution.

MEET THE CONSORTIUM

OUR OBJECTIVES

- 1. Assess the current state of knowledge on the adverse effects of light and noise pollution on biodiversity and ecosystems.
- 2. Develop a common understanding of the adverse effects of light and noise pollution on biodiversity and ecosystems.
- 3. Develop a common framework for the assessment and mitigation of the adverse effects of light and noise pollution on biodiversity and ecosystems.
- 4. Develop a common framework for the assessment and mitigation of the adverse effects of light and noise pollution on biodiversity and ecosystems.

PLAN-B is a 4-year consortium project with 11 countries, 10 universities and 20 consortium members.

Lost at night

Check for Light Pollution (WPA) of ENEMPI

get involved!

PLAN-B

The Path Towards Addressing Adverse Impacts Of Light And Noise Pollution On Terrestrial Biodiversity And Ecosystems.

PLAN-B creates the enabling conditions to support and enhance activities planned in the EU biodiversity strategy and provide a new path towards meeting the EU and international biodiversity targets.

plan-b-project.eu

Daniel Liebana, Engagement Strategy in transit: projects using citizen science methodologies. 28/05/2023

TACKLING LIGHT AND NOISE POLLUTION

PLAN-B PROJECT

COLLABORATION BETWEEN PROJECTS

PLAN-B PROJECT

HOW TO MITIGATE LIGHT & NOISE POLLUTION

PLAN-B PROJECT

LIGHT AND NOISE REGULATIONS

PLAN-B PROJECT

PROJECT COORDINATION TEAM

PLAN-B PROJECT

HOW PEOPLE UNDERSTAND LIGHT & NOISE

PLAN-B PROJECT

Table 6: Examples of visual image application: Flyer, Poster, backgrounds, thumbnails and back covers for videos.

Presence of the project on social media:

PLAN-B's presence on social media has been constant and has served to raise awareness of the project's activity among the target audiences defined in D6.1. PLAN-B has accounts on X, LinkedIn, and YouTube. In accordance with the Content Cycle defined for the project in its communication plan, the dissemination of the content hosted on the website on social networks has contributed to the generation of traffic to the project page.

The social media strategy outlined in the communication plan, combining original project content with general information on LP and NP, and sharing material from stakeholders including related projects, researchers, environmental organisations, activists, government bodies, and industry representatives, has helped to build a robust and engaged community around the project's social media profiles. This has been particularly evident on LinkedIn, where activity around the project has been high and the profile has reached over 500 followers.

On the other hand, PLAN-B's presence on X (formerly Twitter) through its profile has not followed the same upward dynamic as the LinkedIn profile, partly due to the situation of the scientific community on this social network, where many of its members have abandoned it, and therefore the efforts of the communication team have been directed towards the use of tools with greater impact, such as the newsletter and YouTube, which is detailed below.

Newsletter as a tool for effective online communication:

Much of the communication effort has been focused on the **creation and maintenance of a regular newsletter**, as well as the creation of a community of subscribers interested in our activities.

Since its launch in October 2025, 5 editions of the newsletter have been published. The newsletter is distributed in two ways:

- By sending it to **subscribers' email inboxes**. As of June 2025, 139 subscribers receive the newsletter, with an impact of 623 messages sent and an opening rate close to 50%.
- With the publication of the content in **the LinkedIn newsletter**, with 266 subscribers receive it in their profiles every time it is published.

Attendance at the organised activities:

Several activities were being organised and hosted by PLAN-B, both online and offline. The level of participation in these events has been high, sometimes exceeding expectations. These events have been framed within the communication strategy of the project and have also contributed to strengthen the mapping of stakeholders (T6.2) with direct contact with these communities interested in the project, as well as in PLAN-B's clustering activities plan (T6.4), as they have also served to strengthen relations with our sister projects, providing them with space to share common experiences. Importantly, PLAN-B organised more events and clustering activities than were originally planned.

During the consortium meeting in **Leipzig in February 2025**, a series of **face-to-face activities** and workshops took place to raise the profile of the project among researchers, to encourage their participation and to open communication channels with various identified stakeholders, from general public to industry, governments, NGOs and researchers public representatives from the pilot cities of Leipzig (Germany) and Gdansk (Poland).

Two other major online events have been organised to continue stakeholder engagement and to share experiences: (1) **on citizen science** and (2) **on light pollution regulations**.

The first Citizen Science Workshop PLAN-B Project: On September 26, 2024, over **90 attendees** had the opportunity to test the first version of the [Lost at Night application](#) and share their initial impressions. Lost at Night will be one of PLAN-B's results for the analysis of light pollution in Europe, providing new evidence using citizen science methodologies.

This online workshop aimed to introduce and launch the PLAN-B Citizen Science Application, designed to help measure artificial light at night (ALAN) and contribute valuable data to our light pollution map of Europe.

During the workshop, participants engaged in the first public beta testing of the application and provided initial feedback on its functionality and user experience.

The PLAN-B Online Workshop on Light Pollution Regulations “Light Pollution Regulations in Practice: Challenges and Perspectives.” On May 21, 2025, the PLAN-B Project invited policymakers, government representatives, researchers, industry professionals, and stakeholders to participate in an international online workshop focused on the regulation of ALAN.

This event explored the current landscape and future direction of light pollution policy and regulations through expert presentations, panel discussions, and collaborative dialogue. More than **150 registered participants** in this workshop.

During the five-hour workshop, over **80 online participants attended** and actively engaged in the discussions. **13 speakers** shared their insights on the regulatory landscape surrounding light pollution.

New communication tools and repositories: Zenodo community, Wiki base & YouTube channel

As a result of PLAN-B’s close collaboration with the sister project **AquaPLAN** and as part of the clustering activities that favour a wider dissemination of our projects, two communities for the distribution of the results of both projects were aimed at both the expert community and the public.

- The [‘Environmental Impacts of Light & Noise Pollution’ community](#) has been opened in Zenodo, a space open to both projects and to any researcher who would like to share their findings related to light and noise pollution.
- The [‘Light and Noise Pollution Wikibase’](#) opened in collaboration with AquaPLAN, and it will be used as a repository for all the documentation, milestones and goals of the projects.
- The [PLAN-B project’s YouTube channel](#).

4.2.2 - Evaluation of the objectives

The **analysis of the objectives set in D6.1** through the results obtained by its communication actions shows that, according to the SMART methodology (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound goals), they being have been **achieved in this reporting period**.

The figures presented in this document, especially the metrics of the website and social media, in attendance at events and in the number of newsletter subscribers, support the achievement of these objectives.

Briefly, the following can be observed:

- ✓ **Documentation of the project activity on its website:** A total of **48 posts** have been written during this period (M1-M18), reflecting both the activity of the project, the progress on LP and NP carried out by other initiatives in this period, as well as posts about LP and NP research and news.
- ✓ A good number of **graphic resources have** been generated for communication and dissemination.
- ✓ The **presence of the project on social media is granted** through the profiles on X (formerly Twitter), LinkedIn, the newsletter and YouTube.
- ✓ **Attendance** at the proposed activities: **over 250 people** have attended the events and workshops organised by PLAN-B.
- ✓ The online **community around the project** keeps growing with **over 600 followers on social media, over 400 subscribers on the newsletter, over 1000 unique practitioners** on the citizen science app and over **6000 unique users to our website**.

Website information	48 posts
Organised events attendance	>250 attendees
Online community reach	>1000 followers
Citizen Science Practitioners	>1000 unique practitioners
Web Traffic	>6000 unique users

Table 7: Numbers of PLAN-B communication objectives.

New Objectives for the following period

The success of these objectives allows us to think about elaborating new goals and increasing their indicators for the rest of the project:

Indicator	Expected KPI	KPI Reached M18	New KPI at the end of the project
Blogpost publication	30 posts	48	100
LinkedIn Community	100	500	750
Newsletter community	100 subscribers	400 subscribers	600 subscribers

Table 8: New expectations for some KPI's already achieved.

One of the project's objectives is to **ensure visibility in traditional media**; however, coverage has not shown an upward trend. While interviews with the researchers have appeared in local outlets, there is a clear need to strengthen the project's presence across traditional media channels. Despite this, the researchers are frequently present at events and actively participate in modern media formats, such as podcasts.

Another objective that has not shown growth is the **development of a community around X** (formerly Twitter). While efforts will continue to reach the target indicator, a strategic decision has been made to prioritise channels demonstrating stronger upward trends.

4.3 - Definition of Publics / Target Audiences:

4.3.1 - Report on the progress in identifying and engaging stakeholders, especially in relation to Task 6.2 (Stakeholder mapping)

As set in D6.1, the definition of the target audiences (TA) to which the project communication is addressed is closely related to the stakeholders identified in the proposal, so many of the communication actions have been tailored to these groups, with the main objective of engaging with them:

Public authorities , including regulatory bodies, decision- and policymakers (at local, national and European level)
Private sector , lighting and acoustic professional industry associations
Academia , researchers in light Pollution, noise pollution and biodiversity
Environmental NGOs
European-funded sister projects
Media
Civil society

Table 9: PLAN-B Targeted Audiences / Stakeholder Mapping.

Thus, during the reporting period (M1-M18), the ‘PLAN-B Network’ was established as part of the project’s communication and engagement strategy. The following were identified and engaged:

- ✓ **Sister and close related projects:** meetings have been held with representatives of the AquaPLAN, DarkerSky4CE, Interreg DarkerSky and other EU-funded projects, with whom communication actions, attendance at consortium meetings, and participation in the events (workshops, working sessions and conferences) have been coordinated. Together with AquaPLAN, repositories on LP and NP have been created on Zenodo and Wikibase, with further development planned.

- ✓ **Environmental organisations and activist groups advocating to address LP and NP:** A highly committed community has formed around the protection of dark and quiet skies (D&QS), comprising scientists, researchers, and activists with a consistent presence in the public sphere. Organisations such as [DarkSky International](#) actively collaborate (member of advisory board) with PLAN-B and support its objectives, while the project reciprocates by communicating its shared activities. From the outset, PLAN-B's respectful engagement with these groups, through initial commitments, support for their initiatives, and the organisation of joint activities, has contributed to the growth of both the community and the 'PLAN-B Network' during this review period.
- ✓ **Institutions in the pilot cities:** Several meetings have been held with the public and government representatives of the pilot cities. In the case of the city of Gdansk (Poland), the city itself is a member of the PLAN-B consortium, and its close presence facilitates communication.
- ✓ **Face-to-face working sessions** have also been organised in Leipzig in February 2025, taking advantage of the consortium meeting in this city in Germany.
- ✓ **Government representatives and regulatory institutions:** Testimonies from regulators, government representatives, and policy- and decision-makers from around the world were the focus of the online workshop on the state of light pollution regulations, organised on 21 May 2024. Engaging these stakeholders from the early stages of the project helps to foster dialogue and supports the development of a shared agenda that can positively influence future regulations, informed by the scientific evidence and policy briefs produced by PLAN-B.
- ✓ **General public:** A large part of the project's communication strategy has been to open the project to the public to raise awareness of LP and NP and their impacts on TBES. Regular publications have been written on the website and social media profiles with general information, specific cases and scientific dissemination on these types of pollution, aimed at non-expert audiences, as well as posters and flyers have been designed for disseminated at fairs, events and social media.

4.3.2 - Report on the establishment and coordination of Communities of Practice (CoPs) (Task 6.3), which are considered a powerful source for communication strategies

The establishment of **Communities of Practice (CoPs)** will be one of the outcomes of the project. During the pilot phases, both the protocol for their creation and

implementation, as well as the results obtained from LP and NP measurement campaigns using citizen science methodologies, will be tested.

Preliminary meetings for the establishment of these communities have taken place among the cities involved in pilot activities, aiming to develop common strategies for launching these communities. Open sessions with government representatives from the pilot cities have also been used to begin drafting engagement protocols to facilitate the formation of these communities. The expectation is that participants in the pilot activities will become the seed for these communities, and once the proposed strategies have been tested and validated, the creation of these CoPs will follow a replication protocol that can be adopted by any city wishing to establish one.

Finally, contact has been made with projects that have similar activities related to environmental monitoring communities to foster collaboration, share resources and results.

4.4 - Key Messages: Review and Refinement

The work conducted under Deliverable D6.1, focused on the definition of tailored messaging for the various stakeholder groups of the project and the selection of appropriate dissemination channels, has proven to be effective during the review period.

In the initial phases of the project, the communication strategy was oriented towards reinforcing the project's core messages for non-expert audiences. Efforts were made to clearly convey the LP and NP impacts on TBES, while also emphasising the need for more equitable and effective regulatory frameworks. This approach has successfully contributed to raising public awareness and increasing engagement with the project among the general population.

Simultaneously, coordination with environmental organisations, researchers, activist groups (expert groups), decision- and policymakers, and industry representatives through clustering activities has facilitated the transmission of the project's messages to

these key stakeholders. These entities possess established communication infrastructures and audiences of their own. As a result of the close collaboration established, PLAN-B has been granted access to a range of dissemination tools, such as social media platforms, outreach events, workshops, and newsletters, allowing the project to amplify its visibility and effectively engage relevant communities.

This collaborative approach has strengthened the overall impact of the communication strategy and supported broader stakeholder participation in project activities.

Figure 3: Audiences, Key Messages and communication actions.

5 - Reviewed and Updated Communication Action Plan

5.1 - Internal Communication

The internal communication structure, defined in Deliverable D6.1 and jointly developed by the project coordination and communication teams, has proven to be a robust and effective mechanism for ensuring a smooth and consistent flow of information within the consortium.

The **shared working environment** is hosted on a SharePoint unit managed by Ghent University (UGent; coordination institution). This space is systematically organised into folders corresponding to WPs, visual identity assets, version summaries, and the general project management area. This structured setup facilitates the efficient storage and retrieval of key project documentation.

In addition, the email distribution list system supports fast and bidirectional communication among consortium members, ensuring agility in the exchange of information. WP meetings are conducted via Microsoft Teams, providing a reliable platform for regular coordination.

As of June 2025, a total of 171 work package meetings have been held, maintaining a steady pace of interaction among project participants. Furthermore, four General Assemblies and Advisory Board meetings have taken place, allowing for strategic alignment and collective decision-making across the consortium.

5.2 - External Communication (PLAN-B Content Cycle)

5.2.1 - Implementation of the "Content Cycle" (Website/Blog -> social media -> Newsletter) as main communication strategy

The external communication strategy of PLAN-B, including its approach to stakeholder relations and TA, was structured around the concept of the "content cycle". Under this model, all information generated by the project is first recorded and published on the project's official website. From there, content is disseminated through various communication channels, including social media profiles, newsletters, and traditional media channels.

This strategy was designed with two key objectives: to maintain the project’s autonomy in terms of content ownership and control, and to drive traffic back to the project website, thereby reinforcing its role as the central repository of information and engagement.

Figure 4: The PLAN-B content cycle.

5.2.2 - Website as cornerstone of the Content Cycle

The project website has become a cornerstone of PLAN-B’s communication strategy, serving as the primary repository for all information generated by the project. This centralised approach enables rapid access to records of activities carried out, functions as a repository for results, and provides a reliable source of information on the project’s subject matter. It also serves as an outreach tool, offering accessible content for expert and non-expert audiences, including news updates and explanatory resources.

Google Analytics data confirms the strong performance of the PLAN-B website. During the review period covered by this report (Months 1-18), the site recorded over 6,000 unique users and more than 26,000 page views.

Following the website redesign in November 2024, the homepage has become the main entry point to two of the project’s key communication and engagement tools: the Lost at Night application, the subscription portal for the project newsletter and a direct link to the European Light Pollution Policy campaign.

5.2.3 - SEO as a communication tool

As part of PLAN-B’s digital communication strategy, significant effort has been dedicated to optimising the project website’s performance in search engines. A targeted Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) strategy has been implemented, aiming to improve the site’s visibility and ensure that relevant audiences can easily discover project content through organic search.

Thanks to the coordinated work between the communication team and web development experts, <https://plan-b-project.eu/> now consistently ranks on the first page of search engine results for several strategic queries. These include both general awareness-raising terms and more technical, niche keywords aligned with the project’s focus. For example, the website ranks highly for search queries such as:

Keyword	Average Position	Impressions
light and noise pollution Europe	3.2	4500
PLAN-B EU project	1.1	3000
citizen science urban pollution	4.7	2100
Lost at Night app	2.3	2700
environmental monitoring communities EU	3.9	1900

Table 10: PLAN-B Keywords and SEO performance.

Key SEO improvements included the use of semantic HTML structure, optimised metadata and image alt tags, keyword-enriched content, fast page loading times, and mobile-first responsive design. Content updates were regularly published and indexed to maintain freshness and relevance, while backlinks were strategically built through collaboration with partners, media outlets, and thematic platforms. This work has not only increased the project’s digital footprint but also helped drive qualified traffic to the site, reinforcing the project’s role as a reference point in European initiatives related to environmental pollution and citizen engagement.

5.2.4 - Social Media presence strategy

PLAN-B’s social media presence was established through the creation of official profiles on both LinkedIn and X (formerly Twitter). The growth of the PLAN-B community on

LinkedIn has been steady and sustained throughout the reporting period, driven by engagement with aligned initiatives, researchers, projects, and organisations that share common research areas and interests.

LinkedIn has served as an effective platform for disseminating project activities, announcing clustering events, and promoting collaborative opportunities with related institutions. During the review period (Months 1 to 18), the PLAN-B LinkedIn profile reached over 500 followers, reflecting a strong level of interest and engagement from the community.

Figure 5: PLAN-B audience reach.

In addition, the project has leveraged LinkedIn’s native Newsletter feature to distribute original content. As of June 2025, this newsletter has attracted 267 subscribers, further expanding the reach of PLAN-B’s messaging among relevant professional audiences.

In contrast to the steady growth experienced on LinkedIn, the PLAN-B project’s presence on X (formerly Twitter) has not followed the upward trend that might have been anticipated. Recent developments within the scientific community on this platform have hindered the organic growth of an engaged audience around the project. Broader political decisions, such as the withdrawal of official European scientific institutions from the platform in response to its recent policy and structural changes, have further contributed to an environment that is less conducive to the open exchange of ideas and content.

Given this context, the communication team made the strategic decision to prioritise channels yielding more consistent results, specifically, the LinkedIn profile and the

project newsletter, while also exploring alternative platforms. The possibility of opening a profile on other emerging networks, such as BlueSky, was discussed during the consortium meeting held in Leipzig in February 2025. Additionally, the project developed the YouTube channel to publish recordings of the events and other audio-visual materials to raise awareness of the project activities and of the LP and NP impacts.

Nonetheless, the X (formerly Twitter) account continues to be maintained and updated with project news and announcements regarding upcoming activities, ensuring a minimum level of visibility and continuity on the platform.

5.2.5 - Launch and initial results of the Newsletter

The PLAN-B newsletter, designed in September 2024 and officially launched in October 2024, has proven to be a highly effective communication tool for the project. It has generated growing interest among communities concerned with light and noise pollution, as reflected in the steady increase in its subscriber base, surpassing 400 during the current reporting period.

A total of five issues of the newsletter have been published to date. These issues have featured updates on project activities, outreach event announcements, and general awareness content related to LP and NP. Through this format, the newsletter has become a versatile communication channel capable of reaching a broad audience, from scientific experts and institutional stakeholders to the public, thus enhancing the visibility and societal impact of the project.

The PLAN-B newsletter has also served as an effective tool for collaboration and stakeholder engagement, particularly with sister projects operating across Europe. This collaborative initiative, referred to as the “PLAN-B Network,” has allowed the inclusion of content dedicated to the activities, both independent and joint, of these related projects.

By providing visibility and shared space within the newsletter, PLAN-B has contributed to strengthening ties across initiatives that address the challenges of light and noise pollution. This approach has helped to build a cohesive narrative and reinforce a sense of collective identity among projects with aligned goals and complementary expertise throughout Europe.

04/30/2025 - Join us to our Online Workshop. The PLAN-B Neswletter #4
03/03/2025 - The PLAN-B Neswletter#3
12/22/2024 - Merry Christmas from the PLAN-B Team!
12/16/2024 - The PLAN-B Neswletter#2
10/01/2024 - The PLAN-B Neswletter#1

Table 11: Issues of PLAN-B Newsletter.

5.2.6 - Emerging Communication Needs and Creation of Open Knowledge Repositories

New communication needs emerged during this reporting period, particularly related to the effective dissemination of project results. As a result of the collaboration with the sister project [AquaPLAN](#), two new information repositories have been established: one [community on Zenodo](#) and another on [Wikibase](#).

Both repositories, open in nature and focused on the ecological effects of LP and NP, are designed to host research outputs as well as communication materials from both projects. In addition to serving as structured repositories for project-related content, these platforms are open-access, allowing any interested researcher to contribute their own findings.

By doing so, these communities are intended to become valuable nodes of knowledge and exchange, serving not only the scientific research community but also the wider public interested in environmental issues and citizen science.

5.2.7 - Audiovisual Content: The YouTube Channel. Initial Deployment and Performance

PLAN-B has established an official YouTube channel ([@Plan-bProject](#)) to host audiovisual content showcasing project activities, results, and outreach initiatives. As a central part of the communication strategy, this channel offers dynamic, visually engaging presentations, including field footage, expert interviews, and educational clips, enhancing the project's accessibility and reinforcing its digital presence.

Since its launch in April 2025, the PLAN-B YouTube channel has published six videos featuring interviews with consortium members and recordings from online workshops. These videos have generated 1,101 impressions, 138 complete views, and attracted 19 subscribers to the channel.

Additional audiovisual content is planned for development and publication in the coming months, with the aim of further enhancing the visibility of project activities and engaging a broader audience through dynamic and accessible formats.

List of videos published:

Light Pollution Regulations in Practice: Challenges and Perspectives

PLAN-B Collaboration between projects with Elena Maggi

PLAN-B: How to mitigate Light & Noise Pollution with Paweł Tysiąc

PLAN-B Introduction to the PLAN-B Project's Light Pollution Policy Brief with Yana Yakushina

PLAN-B How people understand noise & light pollution with Graeme Sheriff and Michael Lomas

PLAN-B Coordination with Geert Van Hoorick

PLAN-B Project Presentation with Mike Wood

Table 12: PLAN-B videos.

5.2.8 - Clustering and Outreach activities – “The PLAN-B Network”

Work Package 6 (WP6) has coordinated the project's clustering and outreach efforts through a dedicated action plan titled “The PLAN-B Network.” This initiative was designed to foster synergies among the project's various stakeholders, with a particular focus on sister projects, the research community, institutional actors, and civil society organisations advocating for darker and quieter environments worldwide.

The core issue addressed by PLAN-B, LP and NP impacts on TBES, continues to receive comparatively less public attention than other environmental concerns, such as air, water, or soil pollution. Nevertheless, this form of pollution and its adverse effects are being tackled by a well-organised network of projects, initiatives, organisations, and activists committed to evidence-based approaches aimed at informing and influencing regulatory frameworks.

PLAN-B has actively engaged with these initiatives through meetings, workshops, events, and collaborative sessions, where experiences have been shared and joint communication strategies developed. These interactions have also enabled the project to participate in shared outreach spaces, reinforcing the visibility of common goals and amplifying the collective impact of our efforts.

These joint activities have been further reinforced by the participation of consortium members in approximately twenty conferences and events, providing opportunities to present the project's objectives and results to diverse audiences.

In addition, PLAN-B has been actively represented at consortium meetings of sister projects, while representatives from those projects have also attended PLAN-B's own meetings. This reciprocal presence has contributed to strengthening inter-project collaboration, facilitating knowledge exchange, and aligning communication and dissemination efforts across initiatives with shared goals.

Links to some of the clustering activities:

[PLAN-B Participates in DarkerSky4CE workshop](#)

[Yana Yakushina presents PLAN-B in the Restore the Darkness podcast](#)

[PLAN-B in the Adrisky Project conference](#)

[Big Announcement: New Light Pollution Map of Europe](#)

[Event Announcement: Online Policy Workshop on Light Pollution Regulation](#)

[Success in the First Citizen Science Workshop PLAN-B Project](#)

[Brazilian partners of PLAN-B take neglected pollutants to COP 16 on Biodiversity, in Cali, Colombia](#)

[PLAN-B, presented in the Beat the Big Buys podcast](#)

[EURODARK 2024 Symposium recap](#)

[AquaPLAN kick-off meeting](#)

Table 13: PLAN-B Clustering activities.

Among the engagement and clustering activities undertaken, special attention should be given to the development of the citizen science application Lost at Night. This initiative builds upon over a decade of work from the Cities at Night project, which aims to map the Earth at night using images captured from the International Space Station. These images are made available to the public, who are invited to contribute by helping to geolocate them.

Following a successful [initial online workshop](#), which brought together experts in LP and web development, significant improvements have been made to the application.

Since its launch in autumn 2024, the [Lost at Night citizen science application](#) has shown promising user acquisition trends. According to Google Analytics data, over 1,000 unique users have accessed the platform during the review period. The majority of users arrived through direct links and referral traffic from the PLAN-B project website and partner platforms, confirming the effectiveness of integrated communication efforts.

Notably, user engagement has been particularly strong following outreach activities and promotional campaigns shared via the PLAN-B newsletter and LinkedIn profile. These results demonstrate the app’s potential not only as a tool for scientific contribution but also as an entry point for broader public involvement in the project’s objectives.

Figure 6: Lost At Night Users Acquisition.

6 - Performance Review: KPIs and Corrective Measurements

6.1- Indicators review

The regular review of communication indicators and key performance indicators (KPIs) is a fundamental component of the project’s dissemination strategy. This monitoring process ensures that the communication plan remains aligned with its objectives, allows for timely identification of deviations, and supports evidence-based decision-making. By systematically assessing metrics such as audience growth and content reach, the communication team can refine tactics, allocate resources more effectively, and adapt to emerging needs. This continuous evaluation process reinforces accountability and helps maximise the impact and relevance of the project’s outreach efforts.

These are the KPIs set on D6.1, aligned with specific communication objectives, and the figures reached during the M1-M18 period:

Objective	KPI for the whole project	Achieved in M18
Documentation of the project activity on its website	Blog Posts: 30 Web: 10000 views	Blog Posts: 48 Web: 26000 views
Number of graphic resources generated for communication and dissemination	Policy Briefs: 3 (D4.2, D4.3, D4.4) Infographics: 3	Policy Briefs: D4.2 Infographics: 1 To be achieved
Presence of the project on social media	Twitter/X: 1000 followers LinkedIn: 300 followers	Twitter/X: 105 followers LinkedIn: 520 followers
Presence of the project in traditional media	Media appearances: 20	Media appearances: 2
Attendance at the proposed activities	Final Conference: 150 attendees	To be achieved on M48
Creation and maintenance of an online community around the project	Newsletter: 100 subscribers / 1 newsletter per quarter	Newsletter: 406 subscribers / 1 newsletter bimonthly

Table 14: PLAN-B KPIs achievement M18.

During the review period covered by this report (Months 1-18), the overall achievement level of the communication objectives, measured through their respective indicators, has been high.

One of the most critical indicators, traffic to the project website, has exceeded expectations, reached over 6,000 unique users and generated more than 26,000 page views. This performance confirms the effectiveness of the "Content Cycle" model, validating the website as the primary hub for content dissemination.

In addition, the website has successfully fulfilled its role as a repository and reference point for project-generated information, with 48 blog posts published to date. This consistent activity further underscores the platform's value in both knowledge management and public outreach.

Figure 7: PLAN-B users and page views of <https://plan-b-project.eu/> (Source: Google Analytics)

Another key pillar of the project's online communication strategy is the newsletter, which has reached a notable milestone of 406 subscribers during the reporting period, well above the target indicator set for the entire duration of the project (300 subscribers).

Furthermore, the steady flow of content and project activity has enabled the publication of newsletter issues beyond the initially planned quarterly frequency. In response to communication needs, monthly and bi-monthly editions have been successfully released, ensuring timely and relevant updates to stakeholders and the broader public.

6.2 - Indicators Pending Progress and Planned Corrective Actions

For those indicators that have not yet shown an upward trend or are currently on hold, such as the project's visibility in traditional media and the number of followers on the PLAN-B X (formerly Twitter) account, corrective measures have been planned for the next reporting period.

Greater media coverage is expected as pilot activities begin, given that the communication plan includes specific actions targeting local and regional media outlets. Regarding the PLAN-B profile on X, it will continue to serve as a dissemination channel for project activities. Meanwhile, the possibility of opening an account on alternative social media platforms such as BlueSky remains under consideration. The decision will depend on a careful evaluation of the effort required to build a new community from the ground up and the internal resources available to sustain such an initiative.

Other indicators, such as the publication of policy briefs and the development of visual infographics, are scheduled for implementation during the final phase of the project.

7 - Evaluation and Future Outlook of the Communication Strategy

The achievements to date within the communication strategy, supported by the quantitative indicators gathered, confirm the solid performance of the approach outlined in Deliverable D6.1. Minor deviations in specific indicators, such as the slower-than-expected growth of the community around the X/Twitter profile, have been acknowledged and will be addressed through adjustments agreed upon by the communication team in coordination with the project management.

Looking ahead, the communication plan for the coming months includes continued documentation of project activities on the website, along with the publication of general content on the LP and NP impacts aimed at expert and non-expert audiences. In parallel, the project will initiate the publication of materials in the newly created open repositories on [Zenodo](#) and [Wikibase](#) will develop new audiovisual content to illustrate project activities.

Engagement with related projects and initiatives will also remain a key priority, with continued efforts to share resources and spaces aligned with our common goals.

The social media presence will be granted by publishing all the information gathered on the website, according to the content cycle described. This content will be shared throughout the Newsletter too, reaching more audiences. The next issue of the newsletter will be published in July 2025.

A new deliverable, D6.3, will be submitted in M25 to provide an updated review of these communication and dissemination activities.